

Environment

July 2024

The Western Balkans Agenda on Innovation, Research, Education, Culture, Youth and Sport is a long-term strategy from the EU and the Western Balkans (WB) for cooperation with the region. It will contribute to the region's economic and societal development and builds on three main pillars: Political, Thematic, and Regional.

The implementation of the Western Balkans Agenda is monitored by the project POLICY ANSWERS, and the wider context, progress and achievements are summarised in regular reports. In this brief report card, you find the results of the second round of data collection during 2023 and the first months of 2024 and a comparison with the baseline data collected in the previous round.

In terms of Environment, the monitoring focuses on the context indicator "Climate Risk Index" and on a variety of achievements outlined in the WB Agenda (see next page).

Achievements in a wider context of the Western Balkans Agenda

Climate Risk Index

Sources

GermanWatch GLOBAL CLIMATE RISK INDEX 2021. Briefing Paper. <https://tinyurl.com/sourcegw01> (accessed 29 March 2024).
 GermanWatch GLOBAL CLIMATE RISK INDEX 2020. Briefing Paper. <https://tinyurl.com/sourcegw02> (accessed 29 March 2024).
 GermanWatch GLOBAL CLIMATE RISK INDEX 2019. Briefing Paper. <https://tinyurl.com/sourcegw03> (accessed 29 March 2024).

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Regional Indicators

Thematic soil pollution database for the Western Balkans		
--	---	--

Western Balkans Economy Indicators

	Western Balkans Green Agenda implemented		Counteracting climate change & environmental degradation	
	Transition to sustainable transport			
Albania	Only one public initiative in place, no new initiatives			
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Increased number of public initiatives			
Kosovo*	Information not provided			
Montenegro	Information not provided			
North Macedonia	Information not provided			
Serbia	No new hubs established Increased number of partnerships			

Legend: Information not available

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Highlights

JRC regional summer school organised on the evaluation of air, soil and water pollution in support to the European Green Deal

Publication of a comprehensive study in the Environment International Journal about the impact of air pollution on health (mortality and morbidity) in 30 Western Balkans cities

